

STROBE Checklist - Observational Study Protocol

Monitoring the Implementation of the 95-95-95 Strategy in Tshwane: A Quantitative Analysis of Local Progress 2018-2024

Study type: Observational Study (Cross-sectional)

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STROBE Item	Recommendation	Status (Protocol)	Location in Protocol
1	Indicate the study's design title or the abstract	Yes	Title / Abstract
2	Provide informative summary in abstract	Yes	Abstract
3	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Yes	Introduction
4	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	Yes	Introduction
5	Study design described	Yes	Methods
6	Setting described (locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection)	Yes	Methods
7	Participants described (inclusion/exclusion criteria)	Yes	Methods
8	Variables clearly defined	Yes	Methods
9	Data sources/measurement described	Yes	Methods
10	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Yes	Methods
11	Study size explained	Yes	Methods

12	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses	Yes	Methods
13	Describe all statistical methods	Yes	Methods
14	Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study	Not applicable (protocol)	(Results)Not applicable
15	Give characteristics of study participants	Not applicable (protocol)	(Results)Not applicable
16	Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures over time	Not applicable (protocol)	(Results)Not applicable
17	Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision	Not applicable (protocol)	(Results)Not applicable
18	Report other analyses done	Not applicable (protocol)	(Results)Not applicable
19	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	Not applicable (protocol)	(Results)Not applicable
20	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision	Yes (anticipated)	(Results)Discussion
21	Provide a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	Not applicable (protocol)	(Results)Not applicable
22	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Yes (planned)	Discussion
23	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study	Yes	Funding section
24	Give the name of the ethics committee or institutional review board that approved the study, and the reference number	Yes	Ethics section